

A COVID-19 European data set to support training in pandemic management

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Abstract

The PANDEM-2 COVID-19 European training dataset is a large collection of time series associated with indicators on the European pandemic response to the COVID-19 pandemic. It is intended to be used for training in pandemic management.

This dataset is the result of a data gathering requirement process for pandemic management involving feedback and inputs from several public health and first responder professionals as well as researchers directly involved in the European COVID-19 pandemic response. This work is part of the PANDEM-2 project funded by the *Horizon 2020 Secure Societies* program. To collect this data, an open source software was developed named PANDEM-Source allowing reproducibility and customisation of this dataset.

The dataset includes indicators for cases, deaths, hospitalisation, testing and laboratory data including pathogen genomic information, vaccination, non-pharmaceutical interventions, participatory surveillance, social media, human and material resources, flights and contact tracing activities. When no open available data was found, realistic synthetic data and indicators were generated with the goal of producing a data set to be used for pandemic management training.

Background & Summary

PANDEM-2 is an H2020 EU-funded project with the goal of creating innovative approaches to effective pandemic management across the EU. PANDEM-2 aims to better prepare Europe for upcoming pandemics by improving EU member states' capacity for cross-border response through an innovative training platform that includes realistic scenarios. One of the delivered training scenarios is based on the COVID-19 pandemic, which intends to provide useful resources for training public health officers as well as to demonstrate the capacity and gaps in collecting real time data during an ongoing crisis. The COVID-19 training dataset (C19TD) contains all data and indicators used for the COVID-19 use case.

The C19TD was developed in collaboration with several European public health and first responder agencies involved in the COVID-19 response, who were involved in defining a list of variables and indicators to meet present and future demands for pandemic management at national and European level. The list of variables were grouped into the following categories: cases, deaths, hospital capacity, syndromic surveillance, testing and laboratory data including pathogen genomic data, vaccination, contact tracing, participatory surveillance, non-pharmaceutical interventions, population studies, transport, social and mass media.

This data was obtained from traditional surveillance sources among which ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control) and national websites using the COVID-19Datahub [1] R package and Our World in Data [2]. We also include data from non-traditional surveillance such as social media (Twitter), flights (OpenSky Network [3]) participatory surveillance (Influenzanet [4]) and seroprevalence (SeroTracker [5]). Eurostats [6] and OECD reports [7] were used to obtain data from public health resources. When data was not publicly accessible or available, such as contact tracing or public health resources, time series were generated. The generated data does not pretend to be realistic, just to be plausible enough to be used during a training exercise.

Partners involved in the requirement gathering process and the data survey included public health agencies from six National Public Health Agencies in the EU (RKI in Germany, FOHM in Sweden, THL in Finland, INSA in Portugal, NIPH in Romania and RIVM in the Netherlands), first responders organisations (Austrian Red Cross, Italian Red Cross, INEM Portugal and the Radboud Medical Centre, the Netherlands) and the catholic university of Louvain.

Methods

A requirements gathering process was conducted asking partners to provide the most relevant data to guide pandemic management. The answers were analysed to produce an initial list of variables. The list was submitted to participants through a survey to assess the individual data availability and determine the prioritised variables. In parallel, an open data evaluation process was undertaken focused on COVID-19 data sources to determine data availability and the possibility of automated extraction. These elements were combined to produce an automated process of data collection for available variables and synthetic generation for unavailable information. The process is shown in Figure 1.

Selected Sources

The data collection process utilised the following sources for the C19TD

- **Sources Used for Indicators:** Sources used for reporting COVID-19 related indicators and metrics.
 - **ECDC COVID-19 datasets** [8]: Data was extracted from the ECDC COVID-19 reports, which reported countries' national response to COVID-19. Data is collected and published by the ECDC, making it our preferred data source due to the European scope of PANDEM-2. From these reports, we extracted indicators related to confirmed cases, deaths, hospitalisations, and vaccination and government-implemented policies.
 - **COVID-19-Datahub** [1]: An R package capable of producing a unified dataset by collecting fine-grained, global case data from national websites and other sources such as the Oxford policy tracker [10]. This source presents similar data to ECDC but was chosen to generate time series at sub-national level

that were not available on the ECDC datasets. This source was prioritised over other compilations such as the JHU Covid dataset because of the compatibility with ECDC in terms of regional distribution using the NUTS (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics) classification. Indicators extracted from this source included confirmed cases, deaths, hospitalisation, vaccination and testing and contact tracing policies.

- **Our world in data**[2]: Our world in data is a scientific online publication that focuses on global problems. It provides several COVID-19 related datasets. This source was used to obtain extracted excess mortality data since this indicator was missing from previous sources. Reported all-cause mortality data comes from the Human Mortality Database (HMD), the Short-term Mortality Fluctuations project, and the World Mortality Dataset (WMD).
- **InfluenzaNet** [4]: InfluenzaNet is a Europe-wide network to monitor the activity of influenza-like-illness (ILI) with the aid of online volunteers. It is active in twelve countries. In contrast with the traditional system of sentinel networks of mainly primary care physicians, InfluenzaNet obtains its data directly from the population. Data extracted from InfluenzaNet included people with self-reported symptoms and reported visits participants had with any healthcare facility.
- **Twitter, via the Panacea Lab COVID-19 tweet collection** [10]: A large-scale COVID-19 Twitter dataset for open science starting in march 2020. This dataset contains COVID-19 related tweet IDs. We obtained the list of IDs from the data sharing platform Zenodo.org and downloaded the tweet texts using the Twitter API. The tweets were annotated using Natural Language Processing models to produce dedicated time series by country.
- **OpenSky Network** [3]: OpenSky Network is a non-profit association that provides open access of flight tracking control data. It was set up as a research project by several universities and government entities with the goal to improve the security, reliability and efficiency of the airspace. The used dataset is a derived version from the full dataset published on Zenodo covering the period of 2019 to 2022.
- **Eurostat**: Eurostat is the statistical office of the European Union and its mission is to provide a wide range of datasets and statistics concerning European countries. Its data portal contains health resources data sections [11] where statistics relating to hospital resources and staff could be found. Unfortunately, information related to numbers of ICU beds was unavailable.
- **OECD** (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development): The OECD publishes regularly comparable statistics on numerous subjects. In the case of COVID-19 it was the selected source for getting an estimation on the evolution of the number of ICU beds by countries [7].
- **SeroTracker** [5]: SeroTracker is a dashboard and data platform for SARS-CoV-2 serosurveys. It conducts ongoing systematic reviews to track serosurveys (antibody testing-based surveillance efforts) around the world. The results of these seroprevalence studies were integrated into the C19TD.
- **Sources used for standardisation**: To improve reusability and interoperability the use of international standards was prioritised to characterise the time series of indicators.
 - **Eurostat** [11]: The NUTS classification system was used to obtain standardised regional codes. It is a hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU and the UK. The C19TD contains data up to NUTS3 level when available on sources.

- **Geonames.org**[12]: GeoNames is a geographical database distributed under the creative commons attribution licence. It contains over 27 million geographical names. This source was used to extract ISO2 and ISO3 code equivalences and to obtain multilingual aliases for countries and regions in Europe.
- **ICD-10-CM** [13]: ICD-10-CM: The ICD-10 Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM) is a modification of the ICD-10 (International classification of diseases) used as a source for diagnosis codes in the United States of America. This source was used to get the list of pathogens.
- **ISCO-08** [14]: ISCO-08 is a four-level hierarchically structured classification that allows all jobs in the world to be classified into 436 unit groups. This codification was used to store information about resource types in hospitals such as doctors or nurses.
- **Our airports** [15]: OurAirports is a free site where visitors can explore the world's airports, read other people's comments, and leave their own. This site provides freely available files with the list of world airports.

Data acquisition

To enable the integration of all these heterogeneous data sources into a coherent database, a formalism, the Data Labelling Schema (DLS), was defined. The DLS is a declarative method that takes as an input a description of the sources, variables and calculated indicators. This input is provided to a data integration pipeline that uses this information to monitor sources, integrate the data, identify potential errors, and to calculate a set of time series, as an output. This method reduces the chance of errors and ensures that the entire database and its metadata is up to date. Each time series is associated with a source, a unit, a description, a reporting user, a date of integration and standardised attributes. The list of variables can be directly changed to include new measures or indicators if required.

The information required to monitor each source, initiate automatic updates when changes are made, and understand file formats in order to collect data, must be defined in the DLS description of each source. Git repositories, URLs, websites, or custom application programming interfaces (APIs) such as Twitter or Zenodo are some of the acquisition channels that were implemented. The user can implement its own R or Python scripts to carry out the data acquisition if a new channel is required.

The DLS also specifies the target files' formats, which can be Excel, CSV, JSON, or XML. Each format has specific characteristics for interpreting the supplied data. The use of specialised Python scripts to pre-process datasets is supported by PANDEM-Source, if the source is too complex or has to be cleaned before integration.

Natural Language Processing

As social media becomes an important forum for discussing social issues, the surveillance and analysis of its content become a crucial aspect of pandemic management. In this context, the PANDEM-2 project developed social media analysis tools that can be applied to generate time series based on text posted by social media users. PANDEM-Source integrates with these algorithms and produces time series by topic, sentiment, emotion, and suggestions.

For building the C19TD, a subset of 20% of all available COVID-19 tweets from the Panacea Lab was collected. The tweets text were obtained using the rehydrate endpoint of the free Twitter API. This method enabled the efficient retrieval and assembly of a representative

sample of COVID-19 related tweets. Geolocation was performed by detecting explicit mentions of countries or cities on tweet texts. Geographic names and multilingual aliases were obtained from the geonames.org database. The tweets were limited to those related to an EU country. The geonames.org location types were limited to 'country', 'ADM1', 'ADM2', 'PPLA' and 'PPLC'. Each geolocated tweet was annotated using the PANDEM-2 social media algorithms to produce time series by topic, topic and sentiment, topic and emotion, and topic, sub-topic and suggestion.

High-throughput sequencing or next generation sequencing (NGS) for pathogen genome analysis

High-throughput sequencing, also known as next generation sequencing (NGS), has transformed biology and medicine by allowing the analysis of thousands of whole genome sequences (WGS), some of them being accessible in NCBI [16] and GISAID [17]. This breakthrough has enabled real time monitoring of ongoing outbreaks by analysing pathogen genetic evolution (e.g. taxonomy and occurrence of variants, pathogenicity or gain-of-function).

In the context of rapidly evolving infectious diseases, it is necessary to integrate the NGS data with contextual metadata made up biological, clinical, and epidemiological data like age, gender, comorbidities, vaccination status and disease outcome, among which contagiousness, hospitalisation, and death.

This integration should ideally occur during data analysis in order to provide a real-time picture of an outbreak in terms of spread, genetic evolution of the causative agent and its impact on patient comorbidities and disease outcome, as well as assess the efficacy of control measures. There is a limited amount of open-access contextual metadata linked to pathogen sequencing data. Data sharing is hampered by challenges related to patient privacy protection and disparities in data management policies across countries and institutions. We addressed these challenges in order to contribute to the improvement of pandemic preparedness and response through a dedicated training platform.

To this end, a multi-parametric simulation tool that artificially links real or simulated epidemiological, clinical, and biological metadata to the NGS data has been developed (Figure 2) [18]. We developed a R package to run the tool locally, as well as an R-shiny web application [18]. The R Package is available at: <https://github.com/maous1/Pandem2simulator> and the R-shiny application is available at: <https://uclouvain-ctma.shinyapps.io/MultiparametricSimulator/>. Data from ECDC's COVID-19 weekly reports was used to produce time series of confirmed cases by variant, country and age group, as well as hospitalisations by variant, vaccination status and country. The automatic detection of rapidly evolving mutations by country was also explored and included in the C19TD.

Calculated metrics and indicators

Indicators, such as incidence rates, and the effective reproduction number (R_t), are computed using R scripts included with PANDEM-Source. These scripts, used as the final step of the data processing pipeline, work at time series level. They are designed to be easily modified by any user with a basic understanding of the R language. Indicators are automatically calculated when the required parameters are provided on a data source. As an example, each time a source provides numbers of confirmed cases for a region the incidence will be calculated using the region's population which may come from a different data source.

Additionally, automatic aggregation from the subnational to the national level is carried out before indicator calculation. The PANDEM-2 package includes the source code used for each indicator.

Data generation

In the list of variable definitions, PANDEM-Source also incorporates formulas for data generation, enabling the creation of the entire PANDEM-Source datasets with a minimal set of input variables. This data generation feature was designed to generate training datasets that can be used during simulation or functional exercises. In the case of the C19TD this approach was used to produce missing data from open data sources. This includes contact tracing, public health staff variations, syndromic surveillance, and stratification by comorbidities, age groups, and population types. The data generation formulas are defined as simple R scripts, which produce realistic outputs for unknown variables. In cases where partitioned data was missing, such as deaths by comorbidity, a weighted distribution function was applied to the base time series.

As an example, it was assumed that during a crisis the hospital staffing levels would range between 70% and 150% of the original capacity. This variation was calculated based on the ICU occupancy, when the occupancy exceeded 40%. The assumption was that the hospital would be reorganised to face the crisis situation, initially increasing but after 20 days, the staff capacity would start decreasing as long as the occupancy remained above the defined threshold. This logic was implemented as a parametric R script that could be adjusted to match the expected behaviour during a functional exercise.

To avoid potential confusion from having a mix of real and synthetic data in the same dataset, all synthetic time series were labelled with an attribute 'data_quality' set as 'synthetic'.

Data Records

The C19TD dataset can be found on Zenodo [19]. Its content is organised as CSV files and it is divided into two groups, metadata and time series files. (Figure 3)

Metadata files

The C19TD metadata information is stored in three csv.gz files, Indicators.csv, Characteristics.csv, and Dictionary.csv. The Indicators.csv file contains a list of the indicators and metrics from which time series were generated. Each row corresponds to a specific indicator and includes information such as the indicator's name, category, unit, and description. The Characteristics.csv file contains a comprehensive list of attributes used to characterise the time series. Each row provides information about the characteristic name, category, and a description. The Dictionary.csv file records the values that were used for each characteristic. Each row corresponds to a unique value of a characteristic associated with a time series. When characteristics are represented by codes and labels, the *Value* column will contain the code and the *Label* column will contain the associated label e.g. country codes and country names. A list of metadata files and their associated columns is provided below.

- Indicators.csv
 - family
 - indicator
 - unit
 - description

- Characteristics.csv
 - family
 - characteristic
 - description
- Dictionairy.csv
 - Characteristic
 - Value
 - Label

Time Series files

The time series files provide the evolution of each indicator over time, and are named following the indicator names in the indicators.csv file. Rows in time series files provide a value in time for the associated indicator in relation with a set of characteristics such as the COVID-19 incidence in Ireland for a given date and age group. These files have the following columns:

- ts_id: Unique identifier of the time series i.e. all of the data points of a particular time series will have the same id value.
- indicator: The name of the indicator for the time series
- date: The date associated with the data point
- frequency: it refers to the reporting frequency of the time series - it can be daily, weekly, or monthly.
- value: The value associated with the data point
- source: The name of the source where this time series originates i.e. COVID-19 Datahub
- source_file: When sources contain several files or tables this field will indicate the name of the file e.g. *ECDC COVID-19 - ecdc-covid19-weekly-hospital-occupancy*. This is obtained from the DLS definition files.
- data_quality: This is an indicator of the level of confidence in the particular time series. It could refer to official data, compilation, estimated, or simulated data.
- characteristics: separate columns for each characteristic associated with this time series e.g. geo_code, pathogen_code, period_type, vaccination_status

List of indicators

The indicators created using the C19TD are arranged in the table below by group of variables and the quantity of time series made available.

family	variable group	variation	geos	timeserie
cases	active cases	ratio in population time aggregation	1180	2347
	confirmed cases	ratio in population time aggregation	1180	2347
	number of notifications	ratio in population	1180	2347

family	variable group	variation	geos	timeserie
	recovered cases	ratio in population time aggregation	1180	2347
	rt number		1180	2347
deaths	deaths infected	by bed type ratio in hospitalised ratio in population time aggregation	999	1664
	excess mortality	by age group	28	116
hospital capacity	admissions	by bed type by comorbidity ratio in capacity ratio in population	23	36
	available staff	ratio in capacity ratio in population	7	42
	average length of stay		16	16
	hospitalised infected	by bed type by comorbidity ratio in capacity ratio in population ratio with comorbidities	260	813
	number of beds	by bed type ratio in population	389	389
syndromic surveillance	primary care cases		16	48
	primary care positivity	ili vs sari ratio in cases	16	48
testing and lab	performed tests	by test type by variant ratio in cases ratio in population	410	1940
	sequenced samples	by mutation by variant ratio in population	27	3492

family	variable group	variation	geos	timeserie
vaccination	doses injected	by dose number ratio in population	951	2215
contact tracing	contact tracing cases	by being a contact by reached in a day by reached status	693	693
	contact tracing contacts	by reached in a day by reached status	693	693
participatory surveillance	estimated incidence	in 1000 with confidence interval	1180	2336
	number of participants		10	18
	number of visits	ratio in sample	7	82
	participants declaring symptoms		9	18
non pharmaceutical interventions	interventions		1183	8148
population studies	sero prevalence	by study,by study type	25	2869
	studied population size	by study,by study type	25	2869
social and mass media	article count	by topic, sentiment, emotion and suggestion time aggregation	26	6408
transport	incoming flights	by country of origin	26	2225
referential	population	by population type	1373	7636

Technical Validation

The C19TD was developed and created to facilitate the training of public health officials during a simulated exercise of a pandemic. It combines real, simulated and synthetic data, providing a valuable resource for conducting training scenarios and enhancing preparedness for pandemic management. The data quality checks performed are in line with this objective rather than policy formulation or retrospective analysis. To ensure the accuracy of the

provided dataset, several validation processes were implemented. Following the integration of each data source, the resulting time series underwent validation checks for minimum and maximum values. Additionally, a standardised data pipeline was employed to conduct coherence tests on the integrated data, ensuring that only time series with the appropriate format and expected codification were included in the dataset. Furthermore, the integrated and simulated time series were exported to the PANDEM-2 dashboard, where they were visualised and evaluated by expert users during dedicated training sessions. They were further validated during a functional exercise that was carried out in two national public health emergency operation centres. During these instances, valuable feedback was collected from the users, and based on their input, improvements to the calculations were made as suggested. This iterative feedback process allowed for refinements in the dataset, ensuring that the final outputs meet the needs and requirements of expert users.

Usage Notes

This C19TD has been designed to be as simple to use as possible. To complement the information provided on the data record section we provide an example of python code. This code snippet, focused on Germany data, will read and plot the time series for the number of cases of different COVID-19 waves and compare them with the twitter activity and the number of incoming flights from the. To use this code a user must have downloaded the C19TD on the current working directory. The resulting plot is shown on figure 4.

```
import pandas as pd
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt

# Step 1: Reading and scaling cases by variant in Germany
cases = pd.read_csv("01_cases_confirmed_cases.csv.gz",
                    low_memory = False, parse_dates=['date'])
variants = cases[(cases['geo_code'] == 'DE') &
                 pd.notna(cases['variant'])].set_index('date')
variants['legend'] = 'variant ' + variants['variant']
variants['value'] = variants['value']/ variants['value'].max()

# Step 2: Reading and scaling number of posts about Coronavirus topic in Germany
posts = pd.read_csv('11_social_and_mass_media_article_count.csv.gz',
                    parse_dates=['date'])
topic_posts = posts[(posts['geo_code'] == 'DE') &
                    (posts['aspect'] == 'coronavirus') &
                    pd.isna(posts['emotion']) &
                    pd.isna(posts['sentiment'])].set_index('date')
topic_posts['legend'] = 'coronavirus tweets'
topic_posts['value'] = (topic_posts['value']/
                       topic_posts['value'].max()).rolling(7).mean()

# Step 3: Reading and scaling flights from US to Germany
flights = pd.read_csv('12_transport_incoming_flights.csv.gz',
                       parse_dates=['date'])
from_us = flights[(flights['geo_code'] == 'DE') &
                  (flights['country_of_origin_code'] == 'US')].set_index('date')
from_us['legend'] = 'flights from US'
from_us['value'] = (from_us['value']/ from_us['value'].max()).rolling(7).mean()

# Step 4: Concatenating and plotting data
data = pd.concat([variants, topic_posts, from_us]).sort_index()
```

```
data = data[data.index>'2020-02-02'].groupby("legend")["value"]
data.plot(xlabel="Date", ylabel="Scaled value")
plt.legend(loc='right')
plt.title('Evolution of flights from US and social media activity during different
COVID-19 waves in Germany')
plt.show()
```

Code Availability

All the time series contained in the C19TD can be reproduced by using PANDEM-2 software which is distributed using open-source licences such as EUPL-1.2. PANDEM-Source is available on GitHub <https://github.com/pandem2/pandem-source>. To execute the software, Python 3.7+ and R 3.6.3 is required, along with their respective package dependencies as outlined in the project README. During installation, the software will detect and propose suggestions on any missing dependencies. Enabling the NLP annotation features requires additional steps to set up a TensorFlow service and to activate the corresponding models. Detailed instructions for this process can be found in the provided documentation [].

For comprehensive information on PANDEM-Source, the full documentation is accessible in the [PANDEM-2 project repository](https://zenodo.org/communities/pandem-2/?page=1&size=20) [https://zenodo.org/communities/pandem-2/?page=1&size=20].

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Author contributions

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Competing interests

No competing interests

Figures

Figure 1: Requirement gathering & refinement process. Steps followed to define the PANDEM-2 data collection and data generation processes.

Samples from Infected patients

country	year_week	source	new_cases	number_seqenced	variant	number_detections_variant	percent_variant
Germany	2021-03	TESSy	101006	218	B.1.1.7	192	88,1
Germany	2021-03	TESSy	101006	218	B.1.351	24	11
Germany	2021-03	TESSy	101006	218	B.1.525	2	0,9
Germany	2021-04	TESSy	80306	606	B.1.1.7	568	93,7
Germany	2021-04	TESSy	80306	606	B.1.351	26	4,3
Germany	2021-04	TESSy	80306	606	B.1.525	12	2

Country & Time
NGS

Contextual metadata
Derived outcome: SARS-CoV-2 Variant

- Contextual metadata:**
- Age
 - Sex
 - Comorbidities
 - Vaccination
 - Disease outcome (e.g. contagiousness, hospitalisation, death),
 - ...

Figure 2: Illustration of the missing link between contextual metadata and ECDC NGS dataset. The multiparametric simulator is used to simulate this link and produce realistic contextual metadata.

File structure of the COVID-19 EU training dataset

Figure 3: File structure of the COVID-19 EU training dataset

Figure 4: Evolution of flights from US, social media activity during different COVID-19 waves in Germany

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